

The Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center

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USE OF SATELLITE DATA IN HYDROLOGICAL MODEL AND FLOOD PREDICTION

by

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Introduction

The Nansen Center is involved in a 3 year EU project "Applied Remote Sensing and GIS Integration for Model Parameterisation" (ARSGISIP) which is a transnational collaboration by seven Research - End User Teams (RETs) from research organisations and water management agencies.

The general objective of ARSGISIP is to promote the application of remote sensing techniques and GIS integration by demonstrating and verifying the cost-effective implementation of Earth Observation (EO) data for the parameterisation of hydrological, erosion and solute transport models in representative European regions.

ARSGISIP apply standard remote sensing techniques using optical and microwave data. Results obtained will contribute to improve methods for hydrological modelling and prediction as described by Flügel and Müschen (1998). Research has shown that overland flow, erosion and nutrient leaching is generated from source areas distributed over a heterogeneous Vegetation-Soil-Topography Interface (VSTI) within the drainage basin (Bende, 1997; Flügel, 1995).

Properties that control the hydrological dynamics are land use (i.e. land cover and management), topography, geology and soils comprising the VSTI. The latter in turn can be described and quantified by parameters such as slope gradient, aspect, soil moisture, surface roughness or leaf area index (LAI). By exploiting the potential of classification techniques offered by remote sensing integrated into a Geographic Information System (GIS) the resolution and quantification of such parameterisations can be improved.

For Norway this project is especially interesting for development of better flood prediction of rivers such as Glomma. The Nansen Center has therefore defined a demonstration pilot project in Norway, which is described in this report.

Demonstration pilot project in Norway: Flooding in Glomma and Jostedal

Objective

The main objective of the Norwegian pilot project is to demonstrate the feasibility and benefits of satellite remote sensing and GIS techniques in parameterisation for modelling risk factors of flood generation in Norway, with emphasis on change in land use and human impact within the catchment. The long term objective is to use satellite data as an element in flood prediction and management not only for snow but for several other parameters such as vegetation, soil, topography and land use change.

Institutions involved

The project leader is Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Centre (NERSC), for Norwegian demonstration project. Although most of the current activities at the Nansen Center are related to the marine, coastal and Arctic environment, the center is also involved in several projects related to hydrology, geology, vegetation, forestry and other land use. Through these projects, methods of time sequence studies that detect and highlight changes in the terrestrial environment using remote sensing methods are developed (Krzywinski 1990, 1993, 1995, 1998, Babiker 1996, Christensen 1998, Andersen 1998).

In addition to scientists from NERSC, the project includes Geological and Botanical institutes at University of Bergen. The Geological Institute covers national expertise on meso- and macroscale hydrology, Quaternary geology and environmental geology. The Botanical Institute is a national centre of competence on vegetation history and cultural landscape studies with emphasis on land use changes.

The end user involved in this project is the Norwegian Water and Energy Administration (NVE). A major concern for NVE is the increasing incidents of severe floods in Norway throughout the late part of this decennia. Being responsible for inland water management in Norway, NVE has initiated research on

flood and flood prevention (the Hydra Project) aiming at a better modelling of flood and flood risk prevention.

Figure 1: The organisation of the Norwegian demonstration project under ARSGISIP.

Problems to be solved - a new role for satellite data.

Flood prediction and prevention in Norway is not satisfactory, as was obvious during the floods in 1995. NVE's increased awareness of change in hydrological parameters and the increased need for research on aspects of flood prevention in Norway initiated the research program, HYDRA, (which was finished in 1998). The project emphasised the importance of models on flood related to natural resources and land use in the drainage area. However, the HYDRA project did not apply remote sensing data.

Figure 2: Water balance model

So far parameterisation in the most recent hydrological model (i.e. the Hydra model developed by Trond Rinde, SINTEF) is based on conventional mapping and existing thematic maps. Remote sensing has been used for deriving snow parameters, but not for monitoring of geological and hydrological parameters, and the use of historical time series of satellite images to detect relevant landscape changes has not been investigated.

By the application of remote sensing data this project will provide better parameterisation of these variables, and improve the models. Furthermore, analyses of historical time series of satellite images will be applied to investigate relevant landscape changes. Most rural areas in the region have experienced a rapid environmental change due to rural development and change in land use, which has to a large degree altered the traditional flood avoiding measures in rural areas.

The focus of this project is to demonstrate the potential of remote sensing in the derivation and analyses of relevant parameters for the investigation of effects of land use and land use changes on floods. Since local data on actual changes in the hydrological regime is difficult to obtain with sufficient spatial and temporal resolution from other sources, remote sensing provides valuable and indispensable data that gives complete geographic coverage of several key parameters needed in modelling.

In this project remote sensing will be used to derive parameters as vegetation index, vegetation coverage and type, soil surface characteristics and soil moisture. These data can provide input to the analyses of evaporation, interception and precipitation, ponding capacity of soil surface and field capacity.

The project will for the two selected test areas demonstrate the use of time series of remote sensing data to map and quantify landscape changes and their hydrological significance. GIS analyses of derived change images provide a source of information of time sequence data, which can be temporally matched with hydrological incidents. The project aims at providing the end user, NVE, and their research project HYDRA with relevant data for their flood risk model parameterisation.

Study areas

The areas affected by flood regimes in Norway have different characteristics, but are extensive and can have serious impact on regional and national scale. Two study areas, in Østerdalen and Jostedalen, have been selected in this project. The selection is based on differences in land use, vegetation, topography, rainfall pattern and flood regimes.

Test-area 1. The Jostedal catchment (western Norway)

This study area covers a transect from the Sognefjord to a mountainous sub-alpine region, a region characterised by a high rough relief. Changes in land use are very significant. At the present a large impact is imposed on the hydrologic system by hydroelectric development at high altitudes. The hydropower development since the 1970's can have severe impact on conditions for flooding. Furthermore, there is an ongoing transformation of the farming system. Typical for western Norwegian rural system, and other areas in Norway with limited farming areas in the valleys, were small farms at lower altitude and extensive summer farming in the sub-alpine belt. As farming are no longer main occupation within the catchment, the farmers are today less dependent on summer farming in the mountains. These changes in land use can be analysed and quantified by classification of land cover in time series of satellite data. The change in land use will have impact on the hydrological regime and therefore on the possibility to predict and prevent flooding.

Test-area 2. The Østerdalen catchment (central eastern Norway).

This drainage system is part of the Glomma river system, which is the largest in Norway. The relief is characterised by gentle valleys with forests in the hillsides and agricultural fields at the river plain. Land use is in transformation, especially through urbanisation with small towns and centres being erected on former farming land. Changes are also prominent in forestry and agricultural practices. The changes are found in different parts of the local catchments, partly upstream in the hillsides and partly confined to the river plains. These changes have significant impact on the hydrological regimes and therefore on flooding prediction. This area had severe flood in 1995, which showed that insufficient flood prediction can have dramatic consequences.

Work packages

The project started in January 1998 and will last for three years. For each year there will be a number of processed satellite images and a report description of the project work. For the second and third year the EO data will be used as GIS layers.

The project is divided into eight work packages. WP 1 and 2 will be finished in 1998, WP 3-4 will be undertaken in year 1999, while WP 5 - 8 are scheduled to year 2000. During 1998 there has been a process of competence building within the project team, concerning knowledge and skills in hydrological remote sensing and especially methods applied for processing, interpretation and analyses of Landsat satellite images, which is essential for the following work packages in the project. While the computer programs for image processing are relatively easy to use, the qualifications in interpretation and analyses will build on these experiences.

WP1: Project start up, overview of test areas, selection of data, data acquisition: Landsat MSS 1976 scene, topographic data from existing sources and maps.

- In close co-operation with Noralf Rye, University of Bergen, one of the leading hydrologists in Norway, the main study area for the first phase of the project was selected. The project concentrated at the cultural landscape of the Flisa area and the catchment areas of the rivers Glomma and Flisa.

WP 2: Image processing and interpretation of Landsat data, data collection and analyses; fieldwork; topographic data, creation of digital elevation model

- Unsupervised classification of the Landsat MSS 1976 scene, classified with 16, 40 and 80 classes. Selection of training areas for the classes relevant for hydrological modelling and predictions.
- Fieldwork: The first periods of fieldwork in 1998 were used to collect ground truth data for rectification, identification of relevant classes for the classification, and later correction and refinement of the unsupervised classification (based on the unsupervised classification with 16 and 40 classes). Furthermore the fieldwork included data collection from foci of special hydrological significance, hydrological data for reservoirs, discharge and precipitation. The fieldwork in 1999 will be at the same period as the registration of satellite data for the area, in order to ensure optimal possibilities for interpretations and analyses of the satellite images. Two periods of fieldwork is planned for 1999, the

identification and data collection from selected training areas for supervised classification will be completed in the first, the second will be used to check and possibly correct the supervised classification of the images. The collection of ground truth data on vegetation and hydrological data as soil characteristics (surface structures porosity, permeability) will also be completed during the fieldwork in 1999. GPS is used during the fieldwork for exact geographical positioning of observations.

- Digital elevation model based on digital topographic maps. The model combine slope, aspect and hill shade, to define preliminary classes of runoff. The model will later be refined (WP 4) by application of the processed EO data.

WP 3: Data acquisition: Newer Landsat MSS and TM scenes. Processing of data. Interpretations, analyses.

- Unsupervised classification of Landsat MSS 1980 and LandsatTM 1994 and 1999 scenes. Three classification processes (with 16, 40 and 80 classes) to ensure details of land cover data for supervised classification.
- Supervised classification based on selected training areas (unsupervised classified images and ground truth data).Fieldwork for correction of processed images.
- Correction of supervised classification, analyses

WP 4: Digital elevation models, change images, technical report.

- Digital elevation models combined with classified land cover EO data. (Based on the model from WP 2, and classified satellite images).
- Processing of derived change images for intermediate periods. Analyses.
- Technical Report.
- Demonstration for users. Contact with local key-informants and demonstrations for potential end-users of the products.

WP 5: Delineation of classes

- Production of thematic maps, integration into GIS (NVE/EU), GIS analyses of land use and hydrological changes, of EO data and models, groundwater data, historical data on land use and resources, related to modelling and flood predictions.

WP 6: Parameterisation

- Quantification of parameters and variables by end user.

WP 7: Validation

- Verification analyses, cost-benefit analyses
- Demonstrations for end-users, evaluation.

WP 8: Final Report.

Work packages and results 1998

WP	No	Subtask	Scientist	Result
1	1.1	Project start up: overview of test areas, selection of data, data acquisition: Landsat MSS 1976 scene, Topographic data from existing sources and maps. Land use plan for the time periods.	Krzywinski	Project plan and methodology
2	2.1	Image processing and interpretation, data collection and analyses; unsupervised classification, selection of training areas for the classes relevant for hydrological modelling and predictions	NERSC Team 1)	Rectified Landsat MSS 1976 image of Glomma and Jostedal drainage system, (256 values). (Two GIS layers) Classified Landsat MSS scene from Jostedal and Flisa, unsupervised classification with 16, 40 and 80 classes. (16 classes Flisa, fig. 5)

	2.2	Fieldwork: Ground truth data for rectification, refinement of classification, and from foci of special hydrological significance. Hydrological data for reservoirs, discharge and precipitation	Nordgulen and Rye	Geological data in digital form, GPS coordinates for rectification and identification of classes
	2.3	Topographic data, creation of digital elevation model and set up of GIS system (ARC-View)	B. Bodo	Digital elevation model, classes of run-off (Fig.2)
	2.4	Technical report showing progress of the work in 1998.	Krzywinski Bjune Christensen	Technical report

1) NERSC team: Anne Christensen (Cand.polit), Anne Bjune (Cand.scient), Øyvind Dalen (Cand.scient), Balazs Bodo (M. Science), Gidske Andersen (Stud. Cand scient), Gunn Nordgulen (Stud.Cand.scient), Stig Harald Lund (Stud.Cand.scient).

The total work effort in 1998 has been about 1300 hours.

Methods, data and results, 1998

The spatial resolution required by the problem is modified by the requirements of the end user, the resolution of available image material and the work invested. The optimal spatial resolution suggested for the water balance model (Input data: an area units (50/500m) that of the LANDSAT TM for land use classification and that of MSS for change analysis. The temporal resolution is delimited by the availability of cloud free scenes in early summer for the test areas. When possible the acquisition dates are matched with recorded flood events.

For the two study areas not a single one optical scene from 1998 was acquired due to bad weather conditions during the whole summer. Landsat MSS scenes from 1976 (Glomma) and 1978 (Jostedalen) has been processed to serve as the base for the initial fieldwork. Hopefully, cloudless TM scenes will be available in 1999.

The rectification of the Landsat MSS 1976 scene is based on digital and conventional maps in addition to rectification points from field. ER Mapper 5.5.a was used for unsupervised classification of the 1976/1978 images. Classifications with 16, 40 and 80 classes were identified as necessary to make the identification of land cover classes optimal. The interpretation of the classified images was primary based on ground-truth data from fieldwork. The interpretation and classification of the images is a process continuously revised by the ground truth data from fieldwork.

Arcview was used for generation of digital elevation model for Elverum (Glomma area). The model is based on conventional maps, and the classified EO data available are so far not applied.

The products of the first year of the project are rectified Landsat MSS 1976 (RGB) image of the Glomma and Jostedalen areas, rectified and classified Landsat MSS images for the same areas (16, 40 and 80 classes, unsupervised) digital elevation models based on topographic maps with emphasis on factors of influence on hydrological conditions (as slope, shade and runoff), and the present technical report of the progress of work. The deliverables of the 1999 work will be rectified, classified (unsupervised and supervised) Landsat MSS and TM images for 1976 1994 and 1999 (16, 40 and 80 classes) for the two study areas. That is, for each study area there will be 9 GIS overlays from the unsupervised classification of EO data, and three layers of supervised classification (15 classes). Furthermore, the second year of the project will result in an integrated elevation model of classified EO data and topographical data. The data will be analysed in the context of feasibility and benefits of EO data and GIS techniques in the parameterisation for modelling risk factors of flood generation.

The project will deliver end product in the form of GIS overlays of hydrological parameters, land use change and flood vulnerability. The analysis is expected to improve the understanding of local land use change on main hydrological regimes, provide a base for hydrological modelling and improve local and regional flood prevention. The project also produce GIS coverages of satellite images, derived change images and land use change for the by NVE planned GIS database.

Data from Landsat MSS acquired for test areas from 1976 and 1978 (oldest historical scenes available) are now under processing. The data are being prepared for GIS by: (a) rectification of the

scene to a common reference system. (b) Unsupervised classification, editing based on local knowledge of land use, crops, regional patterns and specific features of the area covered by the MSS scene. (c) Acquiring Digital data on elevation and topography from existing maps for the creation of DTEM. (d) Fieldwork gathering data on local hydrology and remote sensing ground truth, including positioned data from selected training areas. The unsupervised classifications of the remote sensing data, the positioned ground truth data, information from consultations of aerial photos and with local key informants will be used for the further refined classification of the image.

The baseline of the project is illustrated in figure 3:

Figure 3: Parameterisation and organisation of factors with effect on runoff and flood

Selection of data and data acquisition

The water-balance model of the end user (the HYDRA model) contain the following parameters:

Tab 1: Important variables of water balance models by the HYDRA project

Water Balance parameters	
Precipitation	P
Temperature	T
Vegetation coverage	VEGCOV
Vegetation height class	VEGHCL
Vegetation type	VEGTYP
Leaf area index for full canopy	LAIMX

Leaf area index in winter	LAIMN
Potential evaporation	POTET
Actual interception capacity in high vegetation	HINTCAP
Actual interception in high vegetation	HINT
Actual evaporation from high interception	AEH
Precipitation that fall through high vegetation	THROUGHFALL
Snow pack	SNOWPACK
Liquid water in snow pack;	SNWWAT
Snow coverage	SNWCOW
Snow melt	SNWMLT
Outflow from snow pack (=SNWMELT + RAIN)	SNOWOOUT
Leaf Area Index in low vegetation	LOWLAI
Interception capacity in low vegetation	lintcap
pounding capacity of soil surface	gropmag
Actual interception in low vegetation and in surface ponds	LINT
Actual evaporation from low interception and surface ponds	AEL
Remaining potential evapotranspiration after AEH is subtracted	REDPOTET ₁
Remaining potential evapotranspiration after AEH and AEL is subtracted	REDPOTET ₂
Precipitation that reach ground	TOSOIL
Field capacity	FS
Soil moisture	SM

Table 2 shows the key parameters of focus for the Norwegian RET team, while table 3 shows the data sources:

Tab 2: The Norwegian RET team focus key parameters related to changes in the hydrologic system.

	Key parameters
Vegetation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VEGCOV, VEGHCL, VEGTYP, LAIMX, LAIMN and LOWLAI
Land use / drainage related change parameters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aforestation and deforestation. • Drainage of forests and wetland • Preparation of land for agriculture. • Urbanisation. • Regulation magazines. • Road constructions railway etc. • Flood protection measurements. • Erosion measurements. • Gravel pits /quarries. • Artificial channelling. • Removal of border vegetation.

Tab. 3: Definition of associated physiographic catchment properties

	Source
Topography terrain, rivers and lakes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • topographic digital maps
Geologic structures /fractures zones	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • geologic digital maps
Distribution of deposits and barren rock	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • geologic digital maps
Infiltration capacity of soil	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • field data and geologic maps
Vegetation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • field data and Landsat MSS and TM images
Permeability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • field data and geologic maps
Deposits type (glacifluvial, fluvial and moraine), distribution and depth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • field data and geologic maps

Image processing and interpretation

Rectification

Unsupervised classification

A classification of the Landsat MSS image is necessary to be able to interpret and analyse the remote sensing data. The steps of the data processing are:

1. Interpret RGB image,
2. Identify the appropriate number of classes
3. Run the unsupervised classification
4. Evaluation of classification, identify classes as ground truth features
5. Supervised classification (future work)

Unsupervised and supervised classification

Multispectral classification is the process of sorting pixels into a finite number of categories of data, or individual classes, based on their file values.

In the unsupervised classification, the classes are determined by the spectral distinctions that are inherent in the data. The unsupervised classification allows you to identify classes that are not in contiguous, easily recognised regions. The unsupervised classification is more computer-automated than the supervised classification, although it allows you to specify some parameters that the computer uses to uncover statistical pattern in the data. Thus, unsupervised classification is dependent upon the data itself for the definition of classes, and it is the analyst's responsibility, after the classification, to attach meaning to the resulting classes.

The supervised classification requires knowledge of the area, and of the set of classes desired, before the classification. The analyst selects pixels that represent patterns or land-cover features that is recognised, and by the identification of these patterns, the computer will identify pixels with similar characteristics.

Interprete RGB image

The first step in the classification process is to look for structures, features and classes of interest in the RGB image. This can be compared to available photos, maps (land-use maps) local knowledge,

Identify the appropriate number of classes

The vegetation types in our test areas differ principally from the ones typical of forested areas further south in Europe. Generally forest areas in Norway are all mixtures and natural or semi-natural in their regeneration. The borders between them are mainly diffuse unless in agricultural and urban areas. In addition, classification of vegetation types varies within disciplines and there exist no universal classification system that can be directly used. This creates a problem for classification of our remote sensing data.

Classes used should be relevant to changes with effect on flood prediction and prevention within the catchment area and will be continuously revised during the process of project work.

Identification of the appropriate number of land cover classes is based on interpretations of the unsupervised classifications of the remote sensing data, ground truth data and consultation of other projects of classifications of land cover (i.e. CORINE Land Cover).

Corrine apply 5 groups of land- cover classes, presented below:

1. Anlagte flater

1.1 By/Tettstedsstruktur

1.1.1 Tett by/tettstedsstruktur (3)

1.1.2 Åpen by/tettstedsstruktur (4)

1.1.2.2. Gårdsbebyggelse

1.2. Industri, handels og transportenheter

1.2.1. Industri og handelsenheter (6)

1.2.2. Vei og jernbanenett med tilknyttede områder (min. Bredde 100 m) (7)

1.2.3. Havneanlegg, kaier

1.2.4. Flyplass (8)

1.3. Gruveområder, deponier og byggeplasser

1.3.1. Massetak/dagbrudd (10)

1.3.2. Deponier (11)

1.3.3. Byggeplasser (12)

1.3.3.1. Demning

1.4. Anlagte flater, bevekste områder

1.4.1. Grønne by/tettstedsareal (parker, kirkegårder mv.)

1.4.2. Idretts- og rekreasjonsområder. (inkl. campingplasser.) (15)

2. Jordbruksareal

2.1. Dyrka mark

2.1.1. Dyrka mark (+ åkerlignende beite) (22)

2.2. Frukt og bærhager

2.2.1. Frukt og bærhager

2.3. Beitemark

2.3.1. Beiteområder (26)

2.4. Heterogene jordbruksarealer

2.4.3. Mosaikk av jordbruksareal med naturlig vegetasjon (29)

3. Skog og seminaturlig mark

3.1. Skog

3.1.1. Lauvskog

3.1.1.1. Lauvskog ikke på myr

3.1.1.1.1. Eldre lauvskog (33)

3.1.1.1.2. Yngre lauvskog (34)

3.1.1.2. Lauvskog på myr (32)

3.1.2. Barskog

3.1.2.1. Barskog ikke på myr

3.1.2.1.1. Tett eldre barskog (over 60 % dekning) (37)

3.1.2.1.2. Glissen eldre barskog (30 - 60 % dekning) (38)

- 3.1.2.1.2.1. Glissen eldre grandominert barskog (39)
- 3.1.2.1.2.2. Glissen eldre furudominert barskog (40)
- 3.1.2.1.3. Yngre barskog (41)
 - 3.1.2.1.3.1. Yngre furudominert barskog (74)
- 3.1.2.2. Barskog på myr (42)
- 3.1.3. Blandingsskog barskog/lauvskog (bar eller lauv ikke over 70 % dekning)
 - 3.1.3.1. Blandingsskog ikke på myr
 - 3.1.3.1.1. Eldre blandingsskog (over 10-15 m) (45)
 - 3.1.3.1.2. Yngre blandingsskog (46)
 - 3.1.3.2. Blandingsskog på myr (47)
- 3.2. Skog og/eller urteprega vegetasjonstyper
 - 3.2.1. Naturlig engvegetasjon
 - 3.2.2. Lyngmark (heivegetasjon)
 - 3.2.2.1 Rishei
 - 3.2.2.2 Grashei (grassnøleie mm.)
 - 3.2.2.3 Lavhei
 - 3.2.4. Overgangsstadiene i skog/busmark
 - 3.2.4.1. Lauvkraut / vierkraut (under 3 m, over 30 % dekning)
 - 3.2.4.2. Hogsflate
 - 3.2.4.2.1. Åpne hogstflater (under 0.5 m, under 30 % dekning) (53)
 - 3.2.4.2.2. Igjenvoksende hogstflater(0.5 - 3 m , over 30 % dekning) (54)
 - 3.2.4.2.2.1. Igjenvoksende furudominert hogstflate
 - 3.3. Åpen mark med ingen/sparsom vegetasjon
 - 3.3.1. Strand, dyner og sandflater
 - 3.3.2. Fjell i dagen / Blokkmark
 - 3.3.2.1. Reguleringssone
 - 3.3.3. Områder med sparsom vegetasjon (57)
 - 3.3.5. Isbreer og snøfelt
 - 3.3.5.1. Isbre
 - 3.3.5.2. Snøfelt

4. Åpne våtmarker

 - 4.1. Ferskvannsvåtmark
 - 4.1.1. Limnogene våtmarker (sumper langs elver og sjøer) (62)
 - 4.1.1.1. Låglend viersump
 - 4.1.1.2. Rik fukteng
 - 4.1.1.3. Takrør - sivaks sump
 - 4.1.1.5. Elvesnelle-starr-sump
 - 4.1.2. Myr (63)
 - 4.1.2.1. Risrik myr (64)
 - 4.1.2.2. Risfattig myr (65)
 - 4.1.2.3. Torvuttak (66)
 - 4.2. Salt/brakkvannsvåtmark
 - 4.2.1 Strandsump
 - 4.2.3 Tidevannsflater

5. Vann

 - 5.1. Innlandsvann
 - 5.1.1. Elver (72)
 - 5.1.1.2. Sand/ grusbanker

- 5.1.2. Sjøer / vann (73)
- 5.2. Marine vannområder
 - 5.2.1. Kystlaguner
 - 5.2.2. Estuarier (gruntvannsområder/tørrfall)
 - 5.2.3. Hav og sjøområder

The final number and type of classes needed to be extracted for our purpose is presented below. This will be the result of the supervised classification, which is based on selected training areas identified in the unsupervised classified image and in field as positioned sites.

- 1 human made areas:
 - 1.1 high density
 - 1.2 medium density
 - 1.3 low density
- 2 forests:
 - 2.1 pine
 - 2.2 spruce
 - 2.3 deciduous
 - 2.4 mixed forest
- 3 cultivated areas:
 - 3.1 crops
 - 3.2 pasture/cultivation
 - 3.3 grass
- 4 water,
 - 4.1 water
 - 4.2 mixed water
- 5. open areas
 - 5.1 herbs/ heather
 - 5.2 barren rock
- 6. snow

Unsupervised classification allows you to define many classes easily, and it may be effective to start with a large number of classes and narrow it through series of classifications. To be able to identify regions or pixels that are representative for the desired classes, the data was classified with 80, 40 and 16 classes.

The 16 classes of land cover in the unsupervised classification of Landsat MSS scenes represents: water, water mixed with stone/grass (bridges, shores of lakes), pine, spruce, mixed forest, deciduous forest, marsh, human made area, different classes of cultivation land (shifting cultivation, pastures, grass) and snow (clouds is present as 3 classes).

To run the unsupervised classification

Ermapper 5.5 was used for the classification of the image.

The images files used for classification are: 213_017.ers and 215_017.ers. The resulting files are presented in the table below.

Tab 4 Files at usr/proj/hydra

	Glomma	Jostedalen
	213_017.ers	
Rectified	213_017_rect.ers	- not rectified
Rectified /classified	213_017_rec_unsuper_10.ers	
	213_017_rec_unsuper_14.ers	

	213_017_rec_unsuper_16.ers	215_017_unsuper_16.ers (preliminary!)
	213_017_rec_unsuper_40.ers	215_017_unsuper_40.ers (preliminary!)
	213_017rec_unsuper_24.ers	
	213_017rec_unsuper_80.ers	
	213_017rec_unsuper_80.ers	

- open ermapper (troll: log in as hydra, >ermapper)
- File -> open -><213_017_rect.ers >
- Process-> Calculate statistic
or check that statistic has been calculated for the dataset: View->Statistic->show statistic-> statistics report box -><OK> -> displayed dataset statistics dialog box is displayed.
- Process menu-> classification-> ISOCCLASS Unsupervised classification ->the box is displayed.
- Input: 213_017_rect.ers
Bands to use: all
Output: 213_017_rec_unsuper_16.ers
Autogenerate 1 classes (default)
Iterations: 100
% unchanged 98.0
Max. number of classes: 16
(see p. 322 Ermapper Reference manual (1995))
- Open classified file.
View menu-> algorithm box-> in left side: check that it is pseudocolour, change the layers->point at pseudo layer, right mouse click – classification layer. (At the right of the box:) Edit-> add raster layer -> class display. Use right mouse click to turn off classification layer, and turn on class display. Open the dataset in layer-><213_017_rect.ers >
- View -> cell values profile. Box is displayed
Use arrow to select pixel in image. Click on “Signature” in box.
Edit-> edit class/region colour and name

Classes and colours:

Tab 5: colours, 213_017_rec_unsuper_16.ers:

Classes	Type	Colours
1	Water	2.35-1.00-35.00
2	Wet areas	23.00 -38 - 42
3	furu barskog	14 - 32 - 2.30
4	gran barskog	16.50 - 41.39 - 3.50
5	mixed forest	16.5 - 44.67- 3.5
6	leaf	18 - 52.04 - 4.5
7	shrub/border vegetation	78.68 - 64.28 - 2.98
8	human made/buildings	50.00 - 8.60-37.00
9	agriculture	66 - 65 - 18
10	agriculture/grass	80.70 - 77 - 45
11	agriculture/grass	85.6 - 82.8 - 42.6
12	pasture	90.98 - 90 - 43.5
13	pine/heather/open	64.75 - 83.60 - 83.19
14	?	82.35 - 82.35 - 82.35
15	clouds	88.24 - 88.24 - 88.24
16	clouds	94.12 - 94.12 - 94.12

Tab 6: colours, 213_017_rec_unsuper_40.ers:

Classes	Type	Colours
1	Water	2.35 1 35
2	Watermix	23 38 42

3	myr	23 44 47
4	Gjengrodd myr?	35.2 29 2.8
5	skog?	32.78 34.4 18.4
6	barskog	14 32 2.3
7	barskog	16.5 39 3.5
8	lauvskog	18 45 4.5
9		
10		
11	slope?	95.5 68.5 9
12		
13	human made, high density	50 8.6 37
14	human made	63.5 8 36
15	agriculture	65 60 1.7
16	agriculture	66 65 18
17	agriculture	66 66 36
18	agriculture	66 65.5 46.5
19	agriculture	65 70 42
20	agriculture	74 77 43
21	agriculture	80.7 77 45
22	agriculture	85.6 82.8 42.6
23	agriculture	90.98 90 43.5
24	grasses	58.6 79 18.85
25 29	lyse flater: human made, lav etc.	"default"
30-40	clouds	"default" – do not change!!!

Figure 4 : Landsat MSS, Flisa area, RGB image with 256 colours

Landsat MSS data has high spectral, but low spatial resolution. As figure 4 shows, this still results in very detailed information of the landcover. However, it is necessary to reclassify the image in order to interpret the data. The unsupervised classification with 16 classes is shown in the figures 5 and 6 below.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5: Unsupervised classification with 16 classes, Landsat MSS, (a) Flisa area, (b) Jostedal area.

Evaluation of classification, identify classes as ground truth features

Selection of training sites

Selection of training sites is so far based on the unsupervised classification of the Landsat MSS scenes and fieldwork in the study area of Glomma. The selection of training sites was in the first hand designed to correspond with the classification with 16 classes. All these classes have now been checked and for some of the classes ground truth data from different sites was necessary for the interpretation of the images. The classes, in particularly agricultural and human made areas, still needs extensive revisions and collection of in situ data.

Figure 6: Flisa area, marked at Landsat MSS classified image and photo. Local scale ground truth data is essential for the interpretation of the earth observation data.

Fieldwork:

Collection of in situ data is essential for interpretation and analyses of the unsupervised classified remote sensing data, for a successive supervised classification of the Landsat scenes, and for the total understanding of the topic and area. During 1998 three periods of field campaigns was performed and successive in situ data for rectification and classification collected. About 14 days was used for fieldwork.

For accurate geographical positioning of the in situ data DGPS was used for in total 38 positions for refinements of the classification. 4 DGPS reference positions was collected for the rectification of the images. The DGPS ensured accurate positioning of rectification points and training areas for classification.

The fieldwork was performed by the two cand.scient students. While the fieldwork in Flisa (Glomma catchment) was directed for classification and interpretations of the remote sensing data, the field-data from Jostedalén have a more general character and includes different variables with influence on the change in flooding potential, as registrations of human made flood protection structures. (The details of the latter fieldwork will be reported later).

The experiences from fieldwork in 1998 create the basis for the establishment of routines:

Problems and routines for fieldwork:

To establish contacts and collect data (maps, interview data) from key personnel at the councils was time-consuming, as the interest of the study was very large, while the knowledge of remote sensing data and GIS so far is rather limited. However, the continued fieldwork (in 1999) will benefit from the time used to establish a network of key contacts.

Since the base of fieldwork was the Landsat MSS 1976 images, the data collected had to be double-checked: observations of land cover was checked with interview data (on change at the particular site during 20 years) and *vica versa*.

Although the selection of training sites was based on studies of satellite images and maps, the access to the areas selected created a problem. Except from the main roads there are a number of private roads, closed for common access. New areas of interest had to be selected, or the closest position possible was registered. In the future, the established contacts will serve to solve the problem of access.

During the first fieldwork, routines for use of field equipment including the GPS, DGPS and antennas was established. Routines for field data registrations was established, i.e. in situ data for rectification points and training areas, as well as interview data from key persons (key personnel at the councils and land use managers (farmers)).

The fieldwork demanded broad knowledge across the sectors of disciplines, i.e. Hydrogeology, Botany and Geography, to identify the classes and sites of interest, and collect data through interviews. Due to the heterogeneous mosaic land cover pattern it is known as difficult to classify the vegetation in field (according to the mixture of species, density and height). Related to the problem of low resolution, scale and the mosaic of land cover it was also necessary to identify homogenous, large areas. This was problematic in particular for the classes of urban areas/ buildings and forests/trees. While some of these classes still need further field data, in particular human made areas, while the selected training areas for the other classes will be applied also for the future fieldwork.

Routines for cooperation between project members

The co-operation between the project members is important. During fieldwork, it is beneficiary to keep regular contact by e-mail and/or phone, to effectively be able to solve any problems by consulting available data from satellite images, maps and ground truth data.

Immediately after fieldwork the data is registered in a common database, the DGPS positioned in-situ data is compared to the classified and rectified images, and the processed satellite image is compared to the ground truth data. Any variance between the classification and the in situ data is analysed, and further project work discussed.

Routines for contact with enduser

NVE, the end-user, is a large and complex institution, and it has been difficult to maintain a regular contact with the end user. The routine for regular contact has to be improved by efforts to strengthen the direct contact with some few key persons.

The digital elevation model and set up of GIS system (ARC-View)

1. Creating a Digital Elevation Model in Arcview

DEM: The idea is to create a continuous representation of elevation values by interpolating point/line elevation data.

Arcview: Step-by-step instructions:

Go to *File* menu. Choose *new project* and add *new view*. Opening an existing vector file. You can open two types of vector files directly in Arcview: shapefiles (*.shp) and CAD files (*.dxf). Click the *Add Theme* button or go to *View* menu's *Add theme* submenu. You can now open shape and dxf files.

The file used to create the DEM is Budapest, C:\kart\k027hol.shp. As you cannot create DEM from polyline files in Arcview (only from points) first you will have to convert the contourlines into a series of points. To do this it is necessary with a plugin (extension) for Arcview, which can be found at Budapest -C:\hydra\ Arcviewextentions\Analys32\

Figure 7 :Conversion of polylines to multipoints:

To create the multipoint shape file: go to the *AnalysisExtention's ConvertShape* submenu and perform the conversion (the options: to convert between polygons, polylines, points and multipoints). Once you have converted the polylines into multipoints you can use Arcview's *Surface* menu's *Interpolate grid* option. You can perform to Interpolation methods (Inverse Distance Weighted-IDW and Spline) using the graphical interface and another two (Kriging and Trend) using Avenue scripts. When using IDW you can choose between the nearest neighbour and the fixed radius options.

Note: The best results were achieved when using IDW with fixed radius although the literature suggests Kriging as a very good option for surface interpolation from contour lines (to do that you will have to get a bit familiar with Avenue).

Figure 8: The DEM created directly from the purchased elevation data over Elverum commune.

The quality of the interpolation is the function of the data density available. The purchased digital elevation data for the primary creation of the elevation model have isolines every 100 meters, and the accuracy is not good. In order to create a more accurate DEM some additional contourlines/elevation points from the paper map available were digitised.

Figure 8 above shows the DEM created directly from the purchased elevation data over Elverum commune. The long "flat" area in the Glomma valley is the result of insufficient data where the entire area between the two 200 meter contourlines on the two sides of the valley was assigned the elevation of 200 meters.

As a large number of further information will be derived from the DEM it is very important to make it as accurate as possible by digitizing additional elevation data where necessary. You will use the DEM to derive:

Slope	Aspect
Sub-catchments	Hillshade

Figure 9 shows the hillshade calculated from the original lower resolution DEM and the increased accuracy after some additional elevation data (elevation along the Glomma river) were subtracted from the 1:50000 paper map of the area.

Figure 9: The hillshade – a) calculated from the original lower resolution DEM; (b) the increased accuracy with additional elevation data.

In Arcview you can very easily derive the slope and the aspect by using the *Surface* menu's option. As the runoff is a function of the slope (besides other parameters) you can reclassify the resulting image into classes. The following classification was used:

<i>Slope in degrees</i>	<i>New cell value</i>	<i>Category name</i>
0-1	1	Low runoff
1-5	2	Medium runoff
5-30	3	High runoff

Note: The accuracy of the primary slope image is rather poor. An accurate DEM is necessary to derive reliable information of for instant the slope

Reclassification can be done in a very simple way in Arcview. Make sure that the theme (image layer) you want to perform the operation is selected and then choose *Reclassify* option from the Analysis main menu. You will have to specify the classification field and the use the classification table to assign new values for the image (see example above). The reclassified slope image shows the runoff potential of the study area as a function of the topography.

Subtracting information from a Remote Sensed image into a GIS.

From the classified satellite image you can get information concerning the landcover which is also in direct relation with the runoff potential. The easiest way to get the data from ER-Mapper to Arcview is to export the dataset into Erdas Imagine format. You can open this directly in Arcview.

Steps:

1. Select the study area in ER-Mapper. Enter the exact coordinates of the area you are interested in by ER-Mappers *Geoposition* menu in the *View* main menu. There choose extents and fill in the corner co-ordinates.
2. Save this new image as a dataset.
3. Go to *Utilities* main menu's *Export raster* and Choose *Erdas Imagine* format.

Notes:

1. Save the image with *.img extension otherwise Arcview will not recognize the file.
2. If you still cannot open check Arcview's *File* menu *Extensions* and see if you have the Imagine file support turned on.
3. Only RGB images in ER-Mapper was converted into Imagine in the initial phase of the project. These reclassified images was saved/print into *.tiff format.
4. To export vectors from ER-Mapper you can choose *.dxf format which you can open directly – without converting- to Arcview.

You should now be able to open your file in Arcview. Check the accuracy of the rectification you did in ER-Mapper by overlaying the purchased vector files on the top of the imported image. It is quite likely that the purchased vector and your imported files will not overlap so you will have to do some geographical transformations in Arcview.

For some reason you can't do any rectification in the 3.0 version of Arcview. Some plugins on the Internet are quite capable of rectifying the images. One of them is the already mentioned Analyst32 extension. With that you can move shapefiles on the top of another shapefile/image by a specified XY coordinates. Just go to the Analysis Extension main menu's *MoveXY* option. You specify the distance in current map units and press OK for performing the transformation. (You can set the map units in *View's* Properties menu.

As the Analysis Extension is a 30-day shareware you will have to reinstall it every month. You can find the installation code/setup in C:\hydra\ArcviewExtensions\Analys32\

Rift is the second software tested, and it seemed to be pretty advanced. Just press the blue diamond button on the main toolbar and you will be asked to specify a "TO" and a "FROM" image plus a ground control point file. You can find a 4 pages detailed documentation of this software and how to install it on other PCs at C:\Hydra\ Arcviewextensions\Rift

Two other freeware plugins are downloaded, but not tested. They are placed at C:\Hydra\ArcviewExtensions\.

When the desired accuracy in the overlapping of data layers is reached, the Imagine/Tiff files have to be converted. To be able to do raster analysis you have to convert them into Arcview grids. Go to *Theme* menu and choose the *Convert grid* option for doing so.

Note: Arcview creates a new sub-directory for each of your grids into the directory you specify. It may be smart to use a temporary directory to store all the grids while you are experimenting, otherwise your working directory will be filled up with garbage very soon.

Once you have converted your files into grids you can start performing some basic GIS operations on them, for instant define new vegetation classes based on positioned and reliable ground-truth data. The example in Figure 10 is an extremely rough estimation of the real landcover based on very limited ground-truth data. The steps are essentially the same.

If you reclassify the landcover image according to the potential runoff then you have created a second GIS layer which holds information on runoff characteristics in the area (the first one was the slope image).

Figure 10: Land cover classes based on ground truth data, processed in Arcview.

Manipulating the data layers.

In the primary phase of the project, two raster layers were made with reference to the runoff. The slope image with values from 1 to 3 representing low and high runoffs and the Landcover image with values from 1 to 5.

Note: The number of runoff classes was kept low to make it as simple as possible. For the continuation of the work it may be a good idea to have for instant 6 runoff categories for each image. You can perform a variety of arithmetic operations in Arcview's *MapCalculator* option. Just go to *Analysis* and choose *MapCalculator*.

If you multiply the two grids in the resulting image you will have cell values ranging from 1 (very low runoff) to 15 (very high runoff). You can decide if you want to keep all these classes or reclassify the image into less categories.

Figure 11: Classes of runoff potential, related to topography, aspect and water drainage system.

Further ideas

Two additional layers are easily created when the data is available.

1. *Geology*. The permeability of the soils can vary in the study region. Areas with low permeable soil will result in higher runoff and areas with high permeable soil will result in a lower runoff. After converting the geology shape files (c:/hydra/geology) into grids you can reclassify the resulting image into new classes with reference to runoff.

2. *Meteorology*. The rainfall and evaporation may vary inside the catchment and should be taken into consideration. Rainfall data from the meteorological stations can be used as input for Arcview's *Interpolate Grid* option to create a continuous surface and then reclassify it.

Note: Changes in topography have more influence on the runoff than the lot smaller changes in rainfall. You should therefore apply different weights to the different factors when overlaying them. It would be quite important to get to know the hydrological model, which will be used for catchment modelling. The output from the GIS should be directly used as an input for the model.

Fig 13: The use of GIS for hydrological modelling

Files and directories.

Budapest, C:\hydra. Do not delete anything on hydra without making backups. The two directories: kart and geology contain the purchased topographical/geological data. In the Arcviewextensions directory you can find all the plugins for Arcview with the relevant setup information. Info,elevgrd and ndvgrd are directories created by the software containing background information. In the directory "report" you will find this document with the name ARSGISIP and all the images that are converted and exported into BMP-s from Arcview.

List and description of the most important files on C:\Hydra:

<i>elevation.*</i>	<i>Elevation contour lines (shp, shx, dxf)</i>
<i>elevpoint.*</i>	<i>Multipoint file converted from the elevation shapefile</i>
<i>elverum.bmp</i>	<i>RGB image of Elverum imported from ER-Mapper</i>
<i>elverum.tiff</i>	<i>The same image in tiff format</i>
<i>elverum3.bmp</i>	<i>The same image but rectified in Arcview</i>
<i>elverum3.bmpW</i>	<i>Documentation file for elverum3.bmp</i>
<i>Ndvi</i>	<i>Bitmap image exported from ER-Mapper</i>
<i>Ndvi</i> points	<i>The above image rectified in Arcview</i>
<i>Ndvi</i> points.bmpW	<i>Documentation file for Ndvi</i> points
<i>Newfile.*</i>	<i>The file with the added elevation values</i>
<i>Pointelev.*</i>	<i>Multipoint file converted from Newfile.*</i>
<i>Runoff.*</i>	<i>The resulting runoff file of the GIS analysis</i>
<i>Water.*</i>	<i>The purchased file of water bodies.</i>

Future work

Year 2 (1999):

WP	No	Subtask	Scientist	Result
3	3.1	Data acquisition: Landsat MSS scene 1980, Landsat TM 1994 and 1999	Krzywinski	

	3.2	Unsupervised classification of Landsat MSS/TM (from 3.1)	NERSC Team	Classified images from time series of scenes from Jostedalen and Flisa Two scenes of each area reclassified to 16, 40 and 80 classes (total: 12 GIS overlays)
	3.3	Fieldwork: Ground truth data from training areas for processing and refinement of the supervised classification. Hydrological field data on soil characteristics. Second fieldwork for test and refinement of supervised classification	NERSC Team and geological Institute, UoB	Ground truth data, contacts
	3.4	Supervised classification based on selected regions from the different unsupervised classified images (16, 40, 80 classes) and ground truth data from fieldwork. Interpretations, analyses	NERSC Team	Three classified images (1976, 1994, 1999) from each of the two study areas, total: 6 land cover GIS overlays
	3.5	Correction of supervised classification. Analyses.	NERSC Team	
4	4.1	Digital elevation models combined with classified land cover EO data.	NERSC Team	Digital elevation model, classes of run-off related to parameters as slope, vegetation type and density, soil
	4.2	Processing of derived change images for intermediate periods, analyses	Krzywinski NERSC Team	Change images
	4.3	Technical report of the 1999 results	Krzywinski NERSC Team	Technical report
	4.4	Demonstrations for NVE	NERSC Team	Feedback from users

The total project work in 1999 is estimated to 1300 hours.

Year 3 (2000):

WP	No	Subtask	Scientist	Results
5	5.1	• Delineation: thematic maps, integration to GIS	Krzywinski, NERSC Team	Thematic maps, GIS overlay
	5.2	GIS analysis and spatial correlation of land use and hydrological changes. (Analyses of EO data and models, groundwater data, historical data on land use and resources, related to modelling and predictions)	Krzywinski NERSC Team	Thematic maps, GIS overlay
6	6.1	• Parameterisation: Quantification of parameters and variables by end user	Krzywinski, NERSC Team	Thematic maps, GIS overlay
7	7.1	• Validation: Verification analyses, cost-benefit analyses	Krzywinski, NERSC Team	
	7.2	• Demonstrations for end-users, evaluation	Krzywinski, NERSC Team	End user evaluation
8		• Final Report	Krzywinski, NERSC Team	Final Report

Time schedule

WP	Task	1998			1999			2000		
1	1.1 Topic, test areas, data selection and acquisition	→								
2	2.1 Image processing interpretation, analyses; unsupervised classification, training areas		→							
	2.2 Fieldwork: data for refinement of classification, and hydrological data			→						
	2.3 Digital elevation model		→							
	2.4 Technical Report				→					
3	3.1 Data acquisition, Landsat scenes				→					
	3.2 Unsupervised classification of Landsat scenes (from 3.1), interpretations, analyses					→				
	3.3 Two fieldwork: Ground truth data for supervised classification, and refinement of this classification						→			
	3.4 Supervised classification, interpretations, analyses						→			
	3.5 Correction of supervised classification, analyses.							→		
4	4.1 Digital elevation models from maps, EO data.							→		
	4.2 Change images								→	
	4.3 Technical Report of results 1999									→
	4.4: Demonstrations for potential users									→
5	5.1 Delineation: Production of thematic maps,									→
	5.2 Integration to GIS (NVE/EU) GIS analysis of landuse and hydrological changes.									→
6	6.1 Parameterisation: Quantification of parameters and variables by end user									→
7	7.1 Validation: Verification analyses, cost-benefit analyses									→
	7.2 Demonstrations for end-users, evaluation									→
8	Final Report									→

Personnel

Name	Tasks	Role	Organisation
Stein Sandven	Project administration	Project manager	NERSC
Knut Krzywinski	Project plan, overview of test areas, selection of data, data	Scientific project leader	Botanical institute, UoB /NERSC

	acquisition, consultant for data processing, analyses and modelling		
Gidske Andersen Anne Bjune Anne Christensen, Øyvind Dalen Gunn Nordgulen	Image processing and interpretations, data analyses; unsupervised/supervised classification, selection of training areas, fieldwork, modelling	NERSC team (G. Nordgulen: UoB, Cand.scient thesis)	NERSC
Balazs Bodo	Digital elevation modelling, integration to GIS, analyses	GIS consultant	Norwegian Research centre /NERSC
Noralf Rye	Consultant for data analyses, modelling and overall assessment and results	Consultant/supervisor Reference group	Geological institute, UoB
Trond Rinde	Hydrological model, consultant on model parameters	SINTEF, modelling, Hydra; Reference group	NVE end-user team
Einar Faugli	External consultant, feedback from enduser	Coordinator Hydra Reference group	NVE end-user team

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